

ECONOMIC SCIENCES

УДК 005.95/.96:621.39

TEAMBUILDING AS A TOOL FOR EFFECTIVE IT- COMPANY MANAGEMENT

Stezhko S.,*State University of Information and Communication Technologies, Kyiv
ORCID 0000-0003-3079-270X***Kondratenko N.,***State University of Information and Communication Technologies, Kyiv
ORCID 0000-0003-3079-270X***Zabolotnia R.,***State University of Information and Communication Technologies, Kyiv
ORCID 0009-0005-7240-034X***Zabolotnii B.***State University of Information and Communication Technologies, Kyiv
ORCID 0009-0009-3112-9513*<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13884401>

Abstract

The article examines the conceptual principles of team building, summarizes the views of various scientists regarding its essence, defines its role and place in the management system of organizations, market relations, and increasing competitiveness. The value of team building as a tool of effective enterprise management, its impact on increasing competitiveness and forming a positive image of the IT company has been studied and summarized. The mechanism of its formation, structure, types and functions are revealed. The influence of the national mentality on the development of team building was identified and substantiated, and its effectiveness was analyzed. Problems and obstacles on the way to the implementation of corporate values are identified and the need for their widespread implementation is emphasized.

The use of team building makes it possible to establish relations within the organization, to organize the harmonious interaction of all members of the work team; increases work efficiency and productivity.

The article also analyzes the advantages and disadvantages of using this method and identifies the main errors during its implementation. The most common types of team building and the main functions of this method are highlighted. The practical application of team building is described on the example of global companies.

Emphasis is placed on the need to use team building as a basis for effective team development, which affects the building of an effective team. The article also provides the experience of using the specified technology.

Conditional stages of team formation and the expediency of using team building methods at all stages of its formation and development are analyzed.

The article examines the conceptual principles of teambuilding, summarizes the views of various scientists regarding its essence, defines its role and place in the management system of organizations, market relations, and increasing competitiveness. The value of teambuilding as a tool of effective enterprise management, its impact on increasing competitiveness and forming a positive image of the IT company has been studied and summarized. The mechanism of its formation, structure, types and functions are revealed. The influence of the national mentality on the development of teambuilding was identified and substantiated, and its effectiveness was analyzed. Problems and obstacles on the way to the implementation of corporate values are identified and the need for their widespread implementation is emphasized.

Keywords: teambuilding, corporate culture, corporate management, competitiveness, competitive advantage, strategic tool, management, image.

1. Formulation of scientific problem and its significance.

The topicality of the topic stems from the fact that in recent years the issue of teambuilding has gained particular importance, attracting the attention of both theoreticians and management practitioners. In the conditions of the formation of market relations, increased competition, globalization and integration of Ukraine into the EU, enterprises are forced to constantly evolve and quickly respond to changes. The driving force in these processes is teambuilding, which unites the enterprise and personnel with a single mission, a single phi-

losophy, development strategy, principles, values, traditions, creates a reputation in the business world, forms the image of the organization, increases its competitiveness and provides a competitive advantage.

2. Analysis of studies of the problem.

Teambuilding as a concept and tool of effective enterprise management was considered in their scientific works by scientists such as O.G. Romanovskyi, V.V. Shapolova, O.V. Kvasnyk, T.V. Hura. The analysis of scientific literature on psychology, management, philosophy, sociology and other sources revealed the absence of a specific date for the use of the term "Teambuilding" for the first time. Some authors believe that

the founder of teambuilding was the author of the Hawthorne experiment (1927-1932), the famous American professor, psychologist and sociologist Elton Mayo, others mention the American researcher and practitioner in the field of organizational development William Dyer, who wrote the first book on of teambuilding in 1977. The analysis of historical sources proves that the first founders of events dedicated to team building and team spirit support were Roman generals of ancient times (approximately 200 BC). In ancient Rome, in order to maintain the morale and cohesion of legionnaires, various physical exercises, competitions for ingenuity, strength and endurance were held. Roman generals tried to create an atmosphere of cohesion among their subordinates and came to the conclusion that there is nothing more effective than play. The following historical figures approached the solution of this question more scientifically: Gaius Julius Caesar (100-44 BC), his descendant Octavian Augustus (63-14 BC), Spartacus (111-71 . BC) etc. They became the founders of a system of means that increase the morale of Roman soldiers based on sports competitions and sports games. The most popular were the Olympic Games, which have not lost their relevance to this day, and have even increased in scale and popularity. Famous American and European leaders such as William the Conqueror (1027/1028-1087), Richard I the Lionheart (1157-1199), Ivan Sirko (1605/1610-1680), Bonaparte Napoleon (1769-1821) and others.

However, it is worth noting that the issue of teambuilding in relation to its impact on the competitiveness of enterprises, the harmonization of industrial relations has not yet received a sufficient systematic analysis in scientific research. The problem of the interaction of competition and teambuilding is still open for development.

3. The purpose and tasks of the article.

The topicality, social significance and lack of scientific development of issues of corporate culture in

terms of its impact on economic indicators, its high theoretical and practical significance determined the choice of topic and task of the article.

Presentation of the main material and substantiation of the obtained research results. In the search for levers to improve the efficiency of the IT team's development and its competitiveness, only economic factors are often emphasized. However, we must not forget that the subject of business is a person. And the result of its work largely depends on it, on its culture, in general, on the culture of the enterprise. Therefore, it is team building that acts as an important factor in the successful operation of the enterprise, increasing its competitiveness. Today, teambuilding is a management tool, one of the progressive methods of managing the workforce.

If until recently it was believed that the strongest wins in the competition, today competitive efforts are aimed at becoming a unique enterprise.

Understanding the essence and development of teambuilding is connected with the transition process of the industrial world in the last third of the 20th century. in the post-industrial. The formation and establishment of teambuilding is an example of how the development of civilization, scientific and technical progress leads society to the need for the development of spiritual culture, the realization that in order to achieve high results in labor activity, only economic methods are not enough, they must necessarily be supplemented by the development of teambuilding. Teambuilding can be considered as a powerful strategic tool, which makes it possible to comprehensively mobilize the forces of the labor team to perform relevant tasks and increase competitiveness.

Today, there is no single approach to the interpretation of the concept of "teambuilding". Analysis of interpretations of these concepts gives reason to conclude that their essence is mostly identical and corresponds to the concept of "teambuilding".

When defining the essence of teambuilding, functional, psychological, and regulatory aspects are often used.

Fig.1. Team Building

Summarizing the given definitions, we can come to the conclusion that teambuilding is specially designed activities aimed at uniting a single, strong and effective team, the members of which are aimed at achieving a single goal, at interaction, complementing

each other, support, respectful attitude and harmonious interaction.

Each successful organization has its own teambuilding features that allow it to stand out among others and create an atmosphere of individuality. Teambuilding acts as an indicator of the development and work of

organizations, because it primarily affects the social and psychological climate, which sets the emotional background for the work of the entire team. It can be interpreted as a management tool that allows you to manage personnel, increase competitiveness, and effectively implement positive changes.

The formation of teambuilding is influenced by the model of socio-economic transformations of Ukrainian society and the Ukrainian mentality. The ethnic characteristics of Ukrainians were formed during a long historical development at the intersection of the influences of different cultures, which were often opposite. This is the dynamic individualized West and the conservative, collective East. Such circumstances affect the formation of the mentality of the Ukrainian people and, accordingly, the peculiarities of teambuilding.

Currently, there is no unified all-Ukrainian view on the past, present and future of teambuilding.

Thus, the well-known scientist V. Hrushko notes: "society will be filled not only with contradictions that paralyze it not only regarding the solution of debatable problems (geopolitical choice, linguistic and cultural policy), but also those on which a national consensus has already been formed, in particular, reforms in the direction of the social market economy" [2, p. 131].

Peculiarities of the Ukrainian national culture, despite some negative features that are due to the historical development of society, are characterized by a number of constructive features of the Ukrainian character, which can contribute to the assimilation of the normative values of teambuilding. We are talking about a high level of development of libertarianism, natural democracy, which can be fixed not only in political, but also in corporate culture. This gives reason to claim that most of the constructive features of the Ukrainian national character can act as important factors in the construction of the management system. We must not forget that freedom-loving combined with a low level of responsibility gives rise to impulsiveness, spontaneity, disorder. Because of this temperament, Ukrainians are inclined towards anarchism and absolutely do not accept despotism.

Therefore, teambuilding is an important factor in increasing competitive adaptability, production and management efficiency. The more actively team building is used, the higher the prestige and competitiveness of the company. Globalization challenges and integration processes significantly expand the competitive field of the subjects of competitive relations and, accordingly, the tasks and approaches to the formation of competitiveness policy and the choice of a modern mechanism for its implementation are changing.

An increasing number of world-class managers state that among the factors that influence the achievement of long-term success by companies, the first place is the human factor, that is, well-chosen, properly organized and motivated employees who know how to effectively build interpersonal relationships and interact with each other and with clients at a high level of cultural communication. Specialists, who studied the factors, that led to the success of the Microsoft company, emphasize,

that the main secret of its success is the creation of a successful corporate environment imbued with a creative spirit, flexible management philosophy and reliance on teamwork. All this is provided by the positive influence of teambuilding. The same can be said about the companies "Honda", "Apple", "Virgin", "Tesla" and others. Their success is determined by values rather than attitude to market forces, rather by the precepts of personal quality than by winning positions in the competitive struggle, rather by concern for understanding the situation rather than problems of resource superiority. Here it is determined that the main value is the person and all attention is paid to him, which contributes to the formation of a high corporate culture. In these companies, there is a steady connection between successful activities and the degree of development of corporate culture. It is its high level that enables them to develop successfully in the conditions of tough competition [12].

Studies of the most successful companies have shown that one of the few factors that distinguish a successful company from a less successful one is the use of teambuilding techniques with clearly defined values. World experience proves that the introduction of corporate culture makes it possible to achieve high levels of organization of the corporation. The more team building is used, the stronger the company is, the more competitive it is, and a powerful corporation is the basis of economic stability.

Evaluating the development of corporate culture in Ukraine, based on the results of sociological research, it is possible to state the following: 55% of modern Ukrainian managers believe that ideally teambuilding should be applied at the enterprise: 40% of our entrepreneurs try to form it with the help of Western technologies; 35% recognize the need for it, but they do not have enough time or resources for it; 25% generally consider it unnecessary [12].

In providing a unique competitive advantage, a special role is played by the use of teambuilding, which refers to the rare and most complex intangible strategic resources that are almost impossible to copy. Teambuilding reflects the uniqueness, inimitability and, as a result, competitive advantages of each enterprise. Teambuilding is one of the most significant strategic resources that provides the enterprise with a sustainable competitive advantage and generally affects the efficiency of its work.

Every enterprise strives to seize the leadership in the competition by its own means. As a result of these actions, the company can gain competitive advantages, which are the basis of competitiveness. Competitive advantage is the guarantee of a strong competitive position of the enterprise and determines the nature of its competitive strategy. Competitive advantages ensure the uniqueness of the enterprise's market position from the point of view of consumers (clients) and business partners. Competitive advantages, as stated by I. Deinega, can be defined "as the high competence of an enterprise in any field, which provides the best opportunities to overcome the forces of competition, attract consumers and retain their commitment to the enterprise's goods. Competitive advantages provide consumers with a product that is of known value to them and for which they are willing to pay money" [3, p. 67].

A fundamental reason for the success of some businesses and the failure of others is that thriving businesses have a competitive advantage that is shaped in large part by the principles of teambuilding.

Today, teambuilding in Ukraine is not always considered as an area that deserves close attention. There are companies that ignore teambuilding altogether, in others the workforce management system is based on the existing corporate culture, and in some companies, measures are taken to change the corporate culture so that it contributes to the implementation of the chosen strategy. Unfortunately, very few Ukrainian enterprises have special services that deal with the formation and implementation of teambuilding. Managers still need time to realize its importance, which can be defined as the intangible basis of competitiveness, the basis of the success of any organization.

4. Conclusions and prospects for further research.

The application of teambuilding is a certain level of mastery, the ability of both staff and management to work effectively at all levels in all functional areas. This means that the efficiency and competitiveness of an enterprise depend mainly on its culture, and therefore, how high or low the level of culture is can be determined by the level of economic efficiency and competitiveness of the enterprise. Low competitiveness and insignificant economic effect indicate that at least one of the structural elements of the enterprise's corporate culture is weak, and the quality of the performance of its assigned functions is low. Therefore, it is the application of teambuilding that determines the level of competitiveness. Today, the process of its formation in the conditions of the market economy and the formation of corporate legislation continues. In order to gain a foothold in the market and increase competitiveness, it is necessary to form a positive corporate culture and, above all, a positive image of your organizations. This is especially important today, when Ukraine's economy has taken a course towards European integration.

References:

1. Anishchenko V.O. The role of corporate culture in management decision-making / V.O. Anishchenko //

Actual problems of the economy. – 2009. – No. 3. – P. 64–71.

2. Hrushko V. The mentality of the Ukrainian people / V. Hrushko // Slavic notes. – Ternopil, 2008. – 218p.

3. Deinega I.O. Competitive advantages as a component of market success. Problems of formation and implementation of competitive policy / I. O. Deinega // Materials of the International Scientific and Practical Conference. – Lviv: "Art-Druk", 2013. – 300 p.

4. Corporate culture of organizations of the 21st century: coll. of science of work / subtotal ed. S. V. Kovalevskiy. – Kramatorsk: DDMA, 2007. – 219 p.

5. Corporate culture: education. manual / G. M. Zakharchyn [etc.] ; under general ed. H. M. Zakharchyn. – Lviv: Novy Svit - 2000, 2011. – 341 p.

6. O. Kravchenko. Corporate culture as a strategic competitive advantage in the enterprise / O. Kravchenko, V. Nikyforenko // Bulletin of the Khmelnytsky National University. – 2011. – Vol. 1, No. 3.

7. Romanovsky O.G., Shapolova V.V., Kvasnyk O.V., Hura T.V. The psychology of team building: a study guide / O.G. Romanovskiy, Shapolova V.V., Kvasnyk O.V., Hura T.V. ; in general ed. Romanovsky O.H., Kalashnikova S.V. - Kharkiv: "Madrid Printing House", 2017. - 92 p. ISBN 978-617-7470-63-1

8. Skibytska L. I. Management: education. manual for universities education closing / L. I. Skibitsky, O. M. Skibitsky. - K.: Center of educational literature, 2007. – 415 p.

9. Chaika G. P. The culture of business communication of a manager: training manual. / H. P. Chaika. - K.: Znannia, 2005. - 442 p.

10. T. Chernyshova Some aspects of the corporate culture of the organization / T.O. Chernyshova, T. A. Nemchenko // Scientific works of KNTU. - Economic sciences. – 2010. – Issue 17.

11. Shevchenko V. S. Determination of the influence of corporate culture on the activity of the enterprise / V. S. Shevchenko // Communal economy. – 2011. – Issue 14. – pp. 160–165.

12. Kishchak T. G. Domestic realities of the formation of corporate culture at enterprises [Electronic resource]. – Access mode: www.economy-nayka.com.ua